

Following the Just Energy Transition in Colombia with CLEW nexus

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Keywords

CLEWs, energy transition, land-use, sustainability, renewable energy.

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Executive Summary

This study employs the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS), selected for its capacity to facilitate Climate-Land-Energy-Water System (CLEWs) interactions. The analysis first explores a Baseline for Colombia, followed by two further scenarios. The Baseline assumes continuity along the current trajectory; the second scenario, follows the actual policy intention of “Just Energy Transition” with 6GW of new renewables by 2026; and the third scenario, includes 100% of electric demand covers by renewables.

The findings underscore a significant challenge: achieving 100% renewable energy electrification necessitates substantial land-use changes, potentially instigating social conflicts over land access. To address this, the report recommends prioritizing distributed generation, implementing robust energy efficiency policies, and fostering citizen involvement through energy communities. Additionally, the analysis suggests that current policy intention alone may not yield a sustained reduction in CO_{2eq} emissions unless accompanied by a shift in the country's approach to new renewable energy investments. The report concludes the significance of the CLEWs nexus in analysing technical data for a sustainable energy transition and integration into policy and decision-making processes.

In summary, this study not only provides critical insights into the challenges and opportunities presented by different energy transition pathways but also underscores the importance of strategic policy decisions, community engagement, and the adoption of advanced modelling frameworks in steering Colombia towards a sustainable and resilient energy future.

1. Introduction

According to the national 2018-GEI inventory for Colombia, land-use changes account for over 60% of emissions, whilst the power sector accounts for 30.7% (IDEAM, 2022). However, most of the climate-national policies are centred on replacing power-plant technologies. Currently, the electric matrix is most of big-scale hydropower (Figure 1) and just 1% of NCRE - Non-conventional renewable energy¹.

Figure 1. Current (2024) % share of installed capacity in Colombia

In the pursuit of a sustainable future, it becomes imperative to understand the intricate interplay between energy transitions, land use, and climate impact. The contemporary discourse on energy policies necessitates a thorough examination of the challenges posed by shifting paradigms in the energy sector. In this context, this research delves into two pivotal aspects that shape the trajectory of the energy landscape: the land-use demand engendered by the energy transition and the climate impact associated with current energy policies (Gobierno de Colombia, 2024).

At the forefront of our inquiry lies the question: What are the discernible impacts on land-use and climate resulting from the ongoing energy transition in Colombia? This research shows the implications for both terrestrial ecosystems and the climate context as an intention of a sustainable energy policy.

2. Methodology

The modelling tool used is OSeMOSYS due its capacity to explore the CLEWs framework. This is an Open-Source long-term modelling tool for the optimization of energy system

¹For Colombia: small-scale hydro power, wind, solar PV, biogas.

investment; according to the restrictions assumed, the tool ensures the minimum cost and highest efficiency in the final decision (Allington *et al*, 2021; Ramos *et al*, 2022; A-B Martindale *et al*, 2023).

Figure 2. Simplified Colombian Reference Energy System

The three scenarios tested are presented in Figure 3.

BAU: Base line	Scenario 1: 6GW	Scenario 2: 6GW + 100% RE
☐ Energy policy continue the same developing	☐ The current government has achieved its goal of 6GW in non-conventional renewables by 2026	☐ The current government has achieved its goal of 6GW in renewables by 2026
☐ The investment in new renewable energy infrastructure is traditional	☐ Hidroituango, a 2.4 GW hydropower project is expected to begin operations in 2024 with 0.8 GW, and 0.2 GW of solar PV and small-scale hydropower	☐ By 2040, 80% of electric demand is renewable
☐ The regulatory framework will not prioritize encouraging distributed energy	☐ By 2025, 1.6 GW, and 0.4 GW of PV and small-scale hydropower	☐ By 2070, 100% of demand comes from renewable
☐ Big-scale hydropower will not have more development.	☐ By 2026, 0.48 GW, and 0.12 GW of solar PV and small-scale hydropower	☐ In this case, the renewable energy regulatory structure needs to be more accommodating than it is now.

Figure 3. Scenario descriptions

Some constrains of the model that distance for the reality:

- The electric demand assumes a tendency of growing population but not increases of demand due to reindustrialization, electric transportation, cooking, or other uses.
- Emissions are assumed for fossil power plants; however, it is already proved that renewable technologies also have GEI associated to its life-cycle (extraction, manufacturing, transport and post-processing) (Nana *et al*, 2014; UN, 2023).
- Water cycle (the balance between precipitation and evapotranspiration, ground recharge and surface run-off) for the land used in the different technologies is assumed as same as build-up.

However, the proportion of evapotranspiration, groundwater and surface run-off could be relatively different between solar PV, wind, and hydropower since the kind of land-use each technology does; for example, hydropower creates an emergent ecosystem while the ecosystem fragmentation in PV is higher and soil properties may be drastically different in contrast with Wind or hydropower. Specific data for this is required for an accurate analysis.

3. Results

The most significant results are presented below, related to installed capacity, power generation, land demand, cost of electricity production and CO_{2eq} emissions. For installed power capacity, the cheapest technology is coal, which is used intensely in the period 2040-2070 by Baseline and Scenario 1 [S1-6GW]. In S1-6GW, the forcing of 6GW of NCRE creates a peak of renewables installed capacity in 2026 but when the lifetime is over, all is replaced by coal and gas. In scenario 3 [S2-100%RE], all electric demand is covered by renewable, but gas remains due to other system uses within a CLEWs model, the simulation uses gas due to high reliability.

Figure 4. Installed capacity

Regarding power generation, that is a variable that considers the capacity factor of technologies. For BAU the hydropower generation remains constant and increases during the year. In the S1-6GW, hydropower remains constant while coal increases considerably before 2050 at a similar rate to gas decreasing until 2070, the use of solar PV is slight in contrast. For S2-100%RE instead, most of the power generation comes from a mix of hydropower at a big and small scale with a tiny increase of solar PV by 2063; is remarkably the diminution of hydropower during a summer session and gradual increase until spring.

In Figure 5, the timeslice for each scenario is presented. This shows the amount of power generated at various times throughout the year. Since the production of renewable energy and the demand for electric energy are influenced by weather and, which is also related to climate variability along the Equator, where Colombia is located, the timeslices depict this variability (much like in South-North regions with seasons).

Figure 5. Power generation detail (upper) and timeslice (below)

The land demanded for power generation in BAU has a maximum of $0.02(10^3)\text{Km}^2$, while in S1-6GW there is a maximum of 0.09, and $2.9(10^3)\text{Km}^2$ in S2-100%RE. For a simple understanding of the dimensions, this proportion in the actual size of Cartagena's city that is 83.2 Km^2 is 80% for BAU; 110% for S1-6GW and 339% for S2-100%RE.

Figure 6. Land-demand for new power sector infrastructure

The Baseline scenario has an almost linear increase of CO₂eq emissions rising 700% between time 50-years estimated; S1-6GW shows a slow increase until 2030, the time in which the 6GW are assumed installed, then start growing almost similar to Baseline arising 670%; S2-100%RE has a peak of emissions in 2040, in which 80% of demand must come from renewables, then decreasing until 36% comparing emissions of 2070 with 2020.

Figure 7. CO₂eq emissions

For all scenarios it is clear that the costs of electricity production are to increase. The Baseline scenario estimates a total increase of 137% between 2020 and 2070; S1-6GW an increase of 126%, the maximum growing rate is presented in the decade of 2020; S2-100%RE has the maximum growing in the decades of 2020 and 2030, and a total of 214%.

Figure 8. Cost of electric production

Here, is relevant to mention that off-shore wind is never used in any scenario regarding the high cost; however, as Colombia does not have any project of this kind and the regulations have not been ready yet, if the current government promote policies for its installation, new simulations could present wind offshore development.

4. Discussion

S2-100%RE requires 118 GW of installed capacity in a mix of solar PV, big and small-scale hydropower, which is 274% higher than the S1-6GW and BAU (both of them has in 2070 a installed capacity close to 43 GW). This is proportional to the huge amount of land demanded in S2-100%RE, following the practical terms, S2-100%RE requires 339 times the actual size of Cartagena, which will likely create pressure over land-access. This is due to the exponential growth of renewables that, while pivotal for a sustainable energy transition, has brought to the forefront an issue that demands careful consideration, especially in regions with high ecological or social value.

For Colombia, the land is a cornerstone of conflict, due its history, big-scale energy projects have been involved with illegal actions. And the conflicts stemming manifest in various forms. Indigenous communities may find their ancestral lands disrupted, affecting their cultural heritage and livelihoods. Agricultural communities face challenges as fertile land is repurposed for solar farms, potentially impacting food security and local economies. Moreover, land acquisitions for renewables projects can lead to displacement and dislocation of communities, exacerbating social inequities, similar as big-scale hydropower created in previous projects.

To address these challenges, it is essential to adopt a holistic approach that balances the imperatives of renewable energy generation with the preservation of ecosystems and the protection of local communities. Integrating environmental impact assessments with social impact assessments can help identify areas of potential conflict and guide the development of solar projects in a more sustainable and socially responsible manner.

Furthermore, engaging local communities in the decision-making processes and ensuring fair compensation for land use can mitigate tensions and foster a collaborative approach to the energy transition. Incorporating principles of responsible land stewardship and sustainable development into renewable projects can help navigate the sensitive balance between meeting energy goals and safeguarding the environment and communities (Ramirez-Tovar, 2022). Ultimately, addressing the excessive land-use associated with renewables requires a nuanced and inclusive approach that prioritizes both the environment and social well-being in the pursuit of a sustainable energy future for Colombia.

Also, a change in land use will potentially increase the GEI emissions if the land-power is located in forestry, as the main GEI source in Colombia is already in the changes of land use. The international commitment of 25% of GEI reduction could be achieved from the energy sector but is mandatory to analyse if the excessive land demand will create repercussions. However, emissions are assumed only for fossil power plants, but it has already been proved that renewable technologies also have GEI associated with their life cycle; is recommended to analyse these emissions for accurate results regarding the climate implications of renewable energy.

The current energy policy proposes a new installed capacity of 6GW for 2026. However, due to the lack of trust in the energy sector of the current administration exists a risk in which the next presidency diminishes the actual “Just Energy Transition” policy. This political risk could represent an incrementation in coal use after 2040. Must because those 6GW represent today 32% of current capacity, what will be 91% of total installed capacity by 2026. Anyhow that “green matrix” demands the adaptation of the future due lifetime of renewables being close to half of fossil power-plant infrastructure.

If renewable investments due not continue, the country will be dependent on energy imports of the region. The simulation recommends coal as the main primary source (the program optimizes the cheaper option), however, is strongly possible that for 2040 the coal was sanctioned by international treatment due to the environmental impact, availability decrease, or the cost of taxes making it unfeasible (Yuanbing *et al*, 2018; Naveed Aslam, *et al*, 2024).

Finally, the difference in costs, particularly capital, between scenarios must be considered. Even when the S2-100%RE has a higher cost, is possible that the cost of

production by Baseline and S1-6GW do not represent a real cost for future carbon-taxes or the increasing cost of coal production.

5. Conclusion

- Achieving 100% of renewable energy electrification will demand several land-use changes (hence creating a social conflict over land access). It is recommended the promotion of distributed generation, a strong energy efficiency policy and citizen involvement, as energy communities.
- The "Just Energy Transition" policy proposed by the actual government will not be going to have a long-term effect on CO_{2eq} decrease if the country does not follow a similar renewables new-inversion behaviour.
- The significance of the CLEWs nexus in analysing technical data for a sustainable energy transition and integration into policy and decision-making processes is simplified under the OSeMOSYS modelling capacities.

In summary, this study not only provides critical insights into the challenges and opportunities presented by different energy transition pathways but also underscores the importance of strategic policy decisions, community engagement, and the adoption of advanced modelling frameworks in steering Colombia towards a sustainable and resilient energy future.

Future work can be focused on estimates, with redefined accuracy, the use of land for other uses. As well as the demand for the electrification of industries, transport, and cooking; include non-direct emissions of renewables (life cycle) as CO_{2eq} per kWh produced.

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